

Greek Partner Services: Standard Operating Procedure

November 2018

Contents

Introduction	3
Purpose	3
Background	3
Definitions.....	4
Indications for PN.....	4
Timing of PN.....	4
Look-back Intervals By Disease	4
Contraindications	5
SGBV assessment:.....	5
Procedure.....	5
Methods.....	5
HIV/STIs.....	5
Overview	5
Detailed.....	6
Viral Hepatitis.....	6
Overview	6
Detailed.....	7
TB	7
Overview	7
Detailed.....	8
Legal	8
National regulations.....	8
GDPR	8
Protecting the Patient.....	9
Interview	9
Tools.....	10
Scripts.....	10
ICT tools	10
Monitoring	10
Annexes.....	11
Annex A: Glossary	11
Annex B: Lookback Intervals	11
Annex C: SGBV Screening Tool.....	12

Annex D: Flowcharts and Infographics	12
HIV/STIs.....	12
Viral Hepatitis.....	12
TB	13
Annex E: Healthcare Professional PN Talking Points	13
Annex F: Patient PN Scripts.....	14
Talking Points for Patients	14
Example Letter for Patient Use	15
Anonymous Example Letter for Patient Use.....	15

Introduction

Purpose

This document describes the standard procedure for partner notification/ contact tracing services in Greece.

The guidelines and recommendations in this manual are not intended to be set in stone. They are designed to be updated and expanded on as necessary and as changes in medical practice and legislation arise.

Background

- To interrupt the chain of transmission for HIV, STIs, viral hepatitis and TB.
- To prevent re-infection of the index patient.
- To identify people that have already been infected and to offer them early treatment, to prevent complications.
- To identify asymptomatic cases and offer appropriate treatment.
- To offer counseling regarding transmission of HIV, STIs, viral hepatitis and TB for people at risk.
- To promote safer sexual and needle-sharing behaviour in persons at risk of infection.

Partner management should be performed as part of prevention programmes together with strategies that help control the spread of disease.

Partner notification can be performed in various settings that deal with sexual health (e.g.: hospitals, clinics, primary care, youth services, community pharmacies) and in various disciplines of medicine (e.g. dermato-venereology, sexual health, primary care, gynaecology, infectious disease physicians).

Benefits for index case:

- Prevention of re-infection.
- Decreasing rate of future infection by appropriate counseling.

Benefits for contacts:

- Providing early treatment for infected contacts, including asymptomatic contacts.
- Preventing complications by offering early treatment.
- Screening for concomitant diseases and offering treatment.

- Decreasing rate of future infection by appropriate counseling.

Benefits for public health:

- Reduction of disease outbreaks.
- Reduction in the period of infectiveness leading to reduced onward transmission.
- Reduction in unsafe sexual and needle-sharing behavior in communities and populations at risk.
- There is little evidence for cost-effectiveness of partner notification due to small number of studies, but early identification, treatment and prevention of complications in infected persons result in cost savings.

Effectiveness of partner notification is assessed according to number of contacts identified, number of contacts traced, number of contacts who tested positive for the infection and number of contacts treated.

Definitions

Partner notification, or disclosure, or contact tracing, is defined as a voluntary process whereby a trained provider asks people diagnosed with an infectious disease about their sexual partners and/or drug injecting partners and then, if the diagnosed patient agrees, offers these partners HTS. Partner notification is provided using passive or assisted approaches (WHO, 2015). In this manual, partner notification will be used in place of contact tracing, even though in some disease areas this will refer to contacting individuals that are not 'partners' of the index patient.

Passive partner notification services refer to when diagnosed patients are encouraged by a trained provider to disclose their status to their sexual and/ or drug injecting partners by themselves, and to also suggest HTS to the partner(s) given their potential exposure to infection.

Assisted partner notification services refer to when consenting diagnosed patients are assisted by a trained provider to disclose their status or to anonymously notify their sexual and/or drug injecting partner(s) of their potential exposure to infection. The provider then offers testing to these partner(s). Assisted partner notification is done using provider referral or dual referral approaches.

Provider referral: With the consent of the infected patient, a trained provider confidentially contacts the person's partner(s) directly and offers the partner(s) voluntary HTS. In many countries, this is only permissible after the involvement of legal or public health committees.

Please see Annex A for a complete glossary of terms.

Indications for PN

Timing of PN

According to the WHO, partner notification services should be offered as part of a comprehensive package of testing and care. While patients should be offered voluntary partner services, it is important to remember that a patient may not be ready to disclose their status upon receiving the diagnosis. For this reason, patients should be offered partner services throughout their interaction with the health system, from diagnosis, to enrolment in treatment, and any follow up visits (WHO, 2016).

Look-back Intervals By Disease

The appropriate look-back interval for partner services should be used. The look-back interval is the time during which the index case may have been infectious and transmitted infection and should be

applied to all contacts whether or not protection was used. The table below lists the infections for which PN should be offered contact actions agreed with the index case, and followed up by a HCW with the appropriate documented competency (Annex B). The corresponding look-back intervals, and whether or not epidemiological treatment of contacts is recommended, is also given. However, these look-back intervals are for guidance. Every case should be assessed on the basis of the sexual history, risk assessment and particular circumstances. There may be benefit in offering PN for some contacts outside these look-back intervals, and justification for not offering PN within the specified intervals.

Contraindications

While partner notification is an important prevention method, there may be situations in which it is not safe for a patient to disclose to their partners. If the patient has any concerns of violence, healthcare workers should utilise the sexual and gender-based violence (SGBV) screening tool from KEELPNO to help assess if partner notification should proceed (Annex C). It is important for healthcare professionals to take into account matters of abuse and the age of legal consent.

SGBV assessment:

With the patient, the healthcare worker/ designated staff member should review any partners where there is a risk or concern of violence. KEELPNO has a SGBV screening tool:

(INSERT TOOL HERE)

Procedure

This section describes the process of partner notification by disease area. It includes an overview of the partner notification pathways, information on the legal restrictions for partner notification, description of the partner notification interview and tools for healthcare providers and patients.

Methods

This section describes the pathways for partner notification in Greece by disease areas. All infographics for the following section can be found in Annex D.

HIV/STIs

Overview

Below is an overview of the PN pathways for HIV and STIs in Greece.

Detailed

Once diagnosed, infectious disease doctors or public health nurses manage partner notification (there is regional variation on this, with PN sometimes managed by other health professionals). In Greece, PN must occur through patient referral. The role of healthcare professionals is to inform patients of the importance of PN and offer support. If patients have trouble notifying their partners, they are referred to psychological services of KEELPNO, which offer support and encouragement for patients to tell their partners. Psychologists use semi-structure interviews to motivate patients, offering information and strategies for PN. Healthcare professionals may assist with partner notification if the patient brings their partner to the office/clinic and is in the room when PN occurs. However, healthcare workers can only assist with PN in person, and may never use letters, phone calls or emails to notify a patient's partner.

PN must be voluntary, except in extreme HIV cases, where doctors can refer the case to the Committee of Legal Support and Legal Problems (KEELPNO), however this is not recommended, and it is unlikely that this is ever utilized.

Viral Hepatitis

Overview

Below is an overview of the PN pathway for viral hepatitis in Greece.

Detailed

HBV and HCV infections are diagnosed in hospitals, blood donation clinics, ID unites, dermatology-venerology departments and private laboratories. Patients are then referred to hepatitis centres and treated in hospitals and outpatient clinics. KEELPNO guidelines ‘Patient Guidelines for Hepatitis B’ and ‘***’ outline the protocol for treating patients and screening partners and contacts.

For HBV, significant effort should be made to examine the whole family: parents, siblings, spouses and children, although the document does not clarify who should do this. For HCV, it is important to notify sexual and needle-sharing partners. KEELPNO does not recommend examining the patients relatives as sexual, vertical and domestic spread of HCV infection is rare.

TB

Overview

Below is an overview of the CT pathway for tuberculosis in Greece.

Detailed

Tuberculosis is transmitted through droplets released into the air via coughs and sneezes and does not require any physical contact to spread disease. For this reason, the process of informing contacts differs significantly in the case of TB. Instead of only notifying sexual and needle-sharing partners, TB contact tracing must also screen household and close contacts of TB patients. The screening and testing guidelines can be found in 'Tuberculosis Case Investigation Protocol' and is managed by public health authorities.

If any healthcare provider suspects a patient has TB, they are legally required to report it under law No. 4053. When diagnosed, both doctors and labs must notify HCDCP by filling out the TB notification form. HCDCP notifies Public Health Directorate (PHD) of the local prefecture and the PHD phthisiology clinic/ local authority is then responsible for local public health action and conducting TB contact tracing. CT usually done in person, occasionally with phone calls, but never with emails. In the case that the patient does not consent to PN, doctors can refer the case to the Committee of Legal Support and Legal Problems (KEELPNO) who may grant permission to perform contact tracing against the consent of the patient.

Legal

National regulations

(Discuss the national and regional laws that govern PN in your country, making clear how staff are legally able to help patients through the PN process).

According to Greek law, partner notification must be voluntary. According the 'Law of Medical Ethics':

....

Ministry of Health 2002 circular 'HIV/AIDS, Public Health and Human Rights':

103. Neither the doctor nor anyone else has the right to announce the HIV-positive person's health condition to his or her spouse or sexual partner, in order to protect them from a potential infection. The HIV-positive person is asked to do so himself/herself, with the provision of psychosocial support, in order that the spouse or partner is also protected.

104. If the HIV-positive person is not persuaded to announce his/her HIV virus infection to his or her spouse or sexual partner, then, after the methods of persuasion have run out, the doctor resorts to the legal committee of the Centre for Disease Control, or the statutory ethics committees or to the hearing prosecutor, who may grant the permission of the announcement if the necessary conditions are satisfied.

Law NO. 4053 'Tuberculosis Declaration':

- Declares all healthcare professionals and organizations must notify HCDCP of any TB, or suspicions of TB.
- TB declarations must be confidential

GDPR

The General Data Protection Regulation 2016/679 is a regulation in EU law on data protection and privacy for all individuals within the European Union and the European Economic Area. It also addresses the export of personal data outside the EU and EEA areas.

Article 9 of the GDPR specifically addresses health data (see below).

Article 9

Processing of special categories of personal data

1. Processing of personal data revealing racial or ethnic origin, political opinions, religious or philosophical beliefs, or trade union membership, and the processing of genetic data, biometric data for the purpose of uniquely identifying a natural person, data concerning health or data concerning a natural person's sex life or sexual orientation shall be prohibited.

The GDPR prohibition on health data, does not apply under certain conditions, such as the following:

2. Paragraph 1 shall not apply if one of the following applies:

(a) the data subject has given explicit consent to the processing of those personal data for one or more specified purposes, except where Union or Member State law provide that the prohibition referred to in paragraph 1 may not be lifted by the data subject;

....

(h) processing is necessary for the purposes of preventive or occupational medicine, for the assessment of the working capacity of the employee, medical diagnosis, **the provision of health or social care or treatment or the management of health or social care systems and services on the basis of Union or Member State law** or pursuant to contract with a health professional and subject to the conditions and safeguards referred to in paragraph 3;

(i) **processing is necessary for reasons of public interest in the area of public health, such as protecting against serious cross-border threats to health** or ensuring high standards of quality and safety of health care and of medicinal products or medical devices, on the basis of Union or Member State law which provides for suitable and specific measures to safeguard the rights and freedoms of the data subject, in particular professional secrecy.

As Greek law does not allow healthcare providers or trained staff to notify a patient's partner (unless in the case of TB), the GDPR does not affect the process of partner notification. It is important to remember that healthcare providers (HCPs)/ trained staff can still inform patients of multiple methods available for their use in PN, including phone calls, emails, ICT tools and other resources. Patients are legally allowed to utilize any of these methods in patient referral, where they notify their partners without the involvement of HCPs.

NOTE: It is important to clarify the legalities of recording/managing partner contact details under the GDPR with your organization.

Protecting the Patient

It is important to make patients aware of their duty to protect future partners from the risk of transmission.

Interview

KEELPNO psychological services use a semi-structured interview to help support patients through partner notification. The Interview for partner notification should include the follow topics:

- I. Introduction
 - a. Introduce yourself
 - b. State purpose/role
 - c. Explain confidentiality

II. Patient Assessment a. Patient Concerns b. Social History c. Medical History d. Disease Comprehension
III. Disease Intervention a. Partner Identification b. Intimate Partner Violence Screening c. Partner Notification Plan d. Risk Reduction
IV. Conclusion and Summary

During the interview, healthcare professionals and designated staff will elicit information about the patients' sex, needle-sharing and close contacts as appropriate. They will assess for sexual and gender-based violence (Annex C) and discuss and establish a partner notification plan with the patient. For additional guidance, more detailed talking points have been provided in Annex E for use by healthcare professionals and designated staff. This script is a guide and may be changed to fit specific needs/ contexts.

Tools

There are many tools available for patients to help them approach partner notification. These tools vary, allowing patients to notify partners through anonymous methods and ICT tools as well as more traditional methods.

Scripts

Whether the patient decides to notify partners in person, via SMS, phone call, letter or email, it can still be difficult to begin the conversation. There are many resources that offer example scripts for patients to use. Annex F includes some examples.

ICT tools

Some key populations may feel more comfortable utilizing ICT tools to notify partners. There are many to choose from, with many allowing the patient to remain completely anonymous. The EU joint action INTEGRATE has created a free online tool which can be found on the website [***](#). Other options, such as websites or apps, can be found in Annex F.

Monitoring

The ECDC recommends monitoring partner notification practices through clinical audits in order to develop interventions that improve outcomes (ECDC, 2015). INTEGRATE experts have suggested gathering data on the following indicators:

- % of patients with PN discussion done
- Proportion of index patients with persistent or recurrent infections

The ECDC also recommends monitoring the following indicators, but there are legal and practical constraints to doing so. Where possible try to gather the following:

- # of partners notified per index patient
- # and proportion of traceable partners per index patient
- # and proportion of partners contacted (mean, reported by index patient)

- # of partners attending clinic per index patient
- # and proportion of partners tested per index patient
- # and proportion of partners infected of the total # of contacts tested
- # of newly infected partners per index patient
- # and proportion of (infected) partners treated of the total numbers of partners infected
- # of partners treated per index patient

For information on TB monitoring, refer to the national guidelines.

Annexes

[Annex A: Glossary](#)

[Annex B: Lookback Intervals](#)

Look-back Intervals by Infection

Infection	Look-back Intervals for PN
Anogenital Warts	6 months
Chancroid	10 days
Chlamydial Infection	Males with urethral symptoms: 4 weeks All other cases: 6 months
Epididymo-orchitis	6 months
Gonorrhoea	Males with urethral symptoms: 2 weeks All other cases: 3 months
Hepatitis A	According to estimated time of infection or 2 weeks before the onset of jaundice If suspected outbreak or concerns of food/water infection, notify local CDC
Hepatitis B 	According to estimated time of infection (via sex or injection) or 2 weeks before the onset of jaundice Screen unvaccinated children born to infectious female index cases.
Hepatitis C 	As far back as estimated time of infection (via sex or injection) if index case and/or contact is HIV positive Ensure any children of female index case are tested.
HIV infection	3 months in recent infection or since last negative HIV test or as far back as required if untested. Ongoing PN should include discussion about testing and re-testing of current partners and testing of children, where appropriate
LGV infection	4 weeks
Non-specific (nonchlamydial, nongonococcal) urethritis in men	Males with symptoms: 4 weeks
Pelvic inflammatory disease	6 months
Phthirus pubis infestation	3 months
Scabies infestation	2 months (including household, prolonged skin-to-skin and bed and clothes sharing contacts)
Syphilis	o Primary syphilis: 3 months o Secondary and early latent syphilis: 2 years

	o Late latent and late syphilis: (of sexual partners and children of female patients) back to the date of the last negative syphilis serology, if available, OR back over the patient's sexual lifetime as far as is feasible.
Trichomoniasis	4 weeks (ISUTI recommends 2 months)

Annex C: SGBV Screening Tool

The following SGBV tool taken from KEELPNO resources

Annex D: Flowcharts and Infographics

HIV/STIs

Viral Hepatitis

TB

Annex E: Healthcare Professional PN Talking Points

Talking points taken from AIDSfree resources

During post-test counselling and/or counselling in the (HIV/STI/hepatitis) clinic:

- Explain the importance of ensuring that all partners get tested for (HIV/STI/hepatitis).
 - (HIV/STI/hepatitis) infected partners can start on (HIV/STI/hepatitis) treatment to keep them healthy and reduce risk that they will pass (HIV/STI/hepatitis) to other sex partners and/or children.
 - Partners not infected with (HIV/STI/hepatitis) can access prevention services to help them remain uninfected, including condoms, pre-exposure prophylaxis (PrEP), and male circumcision.
- Inform the index client that:
 - The clinic is offering Partner Testing Services to assist the client to contact their partners so that these partners can learn their (HIV/STI/hepatitis) status.
 - The service is offered because we know disclosure of (HIV/STI/hepatitis) status to partners can be difficult.
 - Discuss the potential contacts, both sexual and needle sharing, that the patient may need to contact.
- Remind the client of the importance of partner testing using information from above.
- Inform the client that there are options for contacting partners:
 - Client can contact the partner and let them know they should be tested for (HIV/STI/hepatitis);
 - The healthcare providers can contact the partners directly, without telling them the client's name (this will be done anonymously);
 - The counsellor/provider can sit with the client and his/her partner and support the client as he or she tells the partner about their (HIV/STI/hepatitis) infection.
- Inform the index client that:

- All information will be kept confidential. This means that:
 - Partners will NOT be told the index client's name or test results.
 - The index client will NOT be told the (HIV/STI/hepatitis) test results of their partner(s) or whether or not their partner(s) actually tested for (HIV/STI/hepatitis).
- You will NOT contact the partner without first contacting them to get their permission.
- They will continue to receive the same level of care at this health facility regardless of whether they choose to participate in partner notification services.
- Discuss the need to protect future partners from the risk of transmission
- Answer any questions that the index client might have and obtain verbal consent to continue.

Annex F: Patient PN Scripts

Talking Points for Patients

Make a Plan:

- Many people are afraid of telling their partner that they have (HIV/STI/hepatitis). It is helpful to make a plan

for how and when you will tell your partner.

- Think about how you would like to be told, if your partner was disclosing to you.
- Choose a day and a time when you and your partner will have time to talk.
- You also want to pick a time when your partner is not stressed or angry, and has not been

drinking alcohol.

- Pick a private place where you feel comfortable and safe. You may want to have someone in the next room to help and support you, if needed.

Anticipate Reactions:

- Think about how your partner may react. Your partner may:
 - Offer you support or comfort you
 - Not believe it's true
 - Feel confused or sad
 - Feel angry
 - Accuse you of bringing (HIV/STI/hepatitis) into the relationship or household
- Think about how you will respond to these reactions.
- What questions may your partner ask you? How will you answer these questions?

Start the Conversation:

- "I went to the clinic for a check-up the other day [or for xyz reason] and the doctor/nurse was encouraging people to get tested for (HIV/STI/hepatitis). So I got tested and learned that I have (HIV/STI/hepatitis). I wanted you to know so that you could also get an (HIV/STI/hepatitis) test. [If HIV] There are medicines now for treating HIV that can help us live a long time."

- “(HIV/STI/hepatitis) is very common in our community. I decided to go for an (HIV/STI/hepatitis) test. It turns out that I have (HIV/STI/hepatitis). I already started on treatment. I think it is important that you also get tested for (HIV/STI/hepatitis) so you can know your (HIV/STI/hepatitis) status.”

Encourage Your Partner to Get Tested for (HIV/STI/hepatitis):

- Give your partner the Referral Slip
- Tell your partner that it is important they get tested for (HIV/STI/hepatitis). If they have (HIV/STI/hepatitis), they can get medicines to treat their (HIV/STI/hepatitis). These medicines can save their life and reduce the chance they will pass (HIV/STI/hepatitis) onto others.
- If they do not have (HIV/STI/hepatitis), there are things they can do to help them remain uninfected like use condoms, take pre-exposure prophylaxis, or get circumcised (if they are male).
- Offer support because this is difficult news for someone to hear. “We can work on this together. I will support you”.

Practice First!

- Practice what you will say and do ahead of time. You can do that now with your health care provider or later by yourself in your home. This will help you feel comfortable on the day you actually tell your partner.

Example Letter for Patient Use

Here is an example letter for Chlamydia. More STI specific letter examples and fact sheets found at www.letthemknow.org.au .

Dear _____

Since I last saw you I’ve been told that I have Chlamydia. It’s an infection that’s passed on through sex. So, you might have this infection too. Even if you don’t have any symptoms you can still have the infection.

The only way to be sure you are OK is to get tested and treated by your doctor. The treatment is easy and effective.

It’s important to get checked because, if left untreated, Chlamydia can cause long-term health problems such as infertility.

I’ve included a fact sheet on Chlamydia and a letter you can take along to your doctor. If you want to know more you can visit this website www.letthemknow.org.au/partners.html

If you live in _____ call the Sexual Health Infoline on _____ to speak to a sexual health nurse.

Sorry to give you this news but I’m concerned about your health and I thought it was better that you knew.

Regards

Anonymous Example Letter for Patient Use

Here is an example anonymous letter for Gonorrhoea. More STI specific letter examples and fact sheets found at www.letthemknow.org.au .

Dear _____

This letter has been sent to you because someone you have had sex with has gonorrhoea.

Gonorrhoea is a bacterial infection that can be passed from one person to another through sexual contact.

You may have gonorrhoea even though you don't have any symptoms. The only way to find out for certain is to be tested by a doctor.

Gonorrhoea is usually easily treated and we suggest you have the treatment even if your test shows you don't have the infection.

We have attached a fact sheet on gonorrhoea and a letter you can take to your doctor.

Please don't ignore this letter because, if gonorrhoea is not treated it could cause painful medical complications for you. www.letthemknow.org.au/partners.html

If you live in _____ call the Sexual Health Infoline on _____ speak to a sexual health nurse.

Sorry to give you this news but I'm concerned about your health and I thought it was better that you knew.

Regards